

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKIIKI ASIIMWE****FIRST NAME: DEOGRATIAS****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing a good essay (EUCLD 2021, 7-10)
2. American Vs British (EUCLID 2021, 24)
3. Topic formulation (EUCLID 2021, 9)
4. Plagiarism (Helgesson and Eriksson, 2014, 3)
5. The style guide (EUCLID 2021, 41)
6. The grammar (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
7. Proper planning (EUCLID 2021, 8)

DEVELOPING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

The journey for a Doctor of Philosophy in Diplomatic Relations started with a burning zeal in 2022 when I participated in the United Nations Conference. Based on the papers that were presented by the participants, I felt urged to advance my studies so as to acquire more skills and knowledge about concept paper writing and presentation.

It is upon this that I found my way to EUCLD University to pursue my dream. Upon admission, I was nervous about completion and progress because of the intensity of the materials for reading and videos for tutorials for watching. This propelled me to work harder so as to meet the expected deadlines.

Upon reading the first course material (ACA-401D Period 1), it was capturing, interesting, and appealing for continued interaction with the material. This is because it introduces you to the format of how to write a good essay, the punctuation marks, the English to be used, the style of writing, and precautions before submission.

Despite my anxiety and related fears, I have been able to read the material written by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck (International Faculty Coordinator) and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (Course Instructor) and have been able to watch tutorial videos about heading formatting styles and writing techniques as presented in Basic ACA-401 Tutorial video clip.

Therefore, I now have the courage to face the reality of academic writing using the Zotero and Turabian format of writing. Through this experience, I expect to be one of the best academic writers based on my first writing experience with Euclid University.

In this response paper, my discussion will be based on essay writing, plagiarism, some rules of thumb writing, style of writing, and American VS British language style.

2) GENERAL BACKGROUND TO EASY WRITING

In the first chapter of the study material ACA-401D Period 1, the course pack elaborates on the initial guidelines that are recommended to come up with a good essay. This is because the materials prepare the student and equip him or her with the basics and tips about the introduction, body, and conclusion of an essay.

In addition, I have observed that there is a need for adequate planning so as to write a quality paper. This calls for a lot of commitment embedded with setting aside extra time to comprehensively write a good paper (EUCLID 2021, 8). This is achievable through having a proper strategic plan, which will help the student stay steadfast and organized while executing the task beforehand.

An academic essay is primarily intended to address a particular phenomenon in a particular situation. For any of these papers to be called academic, there is a need for scholarly evidence that one can base on to qualify the assertion (EUCLID 2021, 7). I concur with this assertion because, in most instances, the subjects written about are not new, and the researcher must not assume that he or she is making a fresh invention. Therefore, since one is building on already existing knowledge based on existing literature, there is a need to acknowledge those sources in the text.

Furthermore, the student needs to always take notes as he or she interacts with any research materials. This helps one to keep useful information that can be referred to during the process of writing. The information to be kept includes authors, publishing places, the date/year, and the page numbers, which will be used to form a reference list.

There is a need for the formulation of a relevant and researchable topic. This topic should be simple, realistic, and address a particular problem (EUCLID 2021, 9). For any paper to be organized, there must be a clear structure to follow. This structure of the essay is followed by the introduction, body, and conclusion. This helps in communicating the message clearly and articulately while negating inconsistencies and ambiguity (EUCLID 2021, 10).

About the English to be used in the study, the researcher should know the type of English, either American or British English versions (EUCLID 2021, 24). This is because they have different styles and spellings in some words. So, the researcher has to be keen on this aspect. However, I personally find it challenging, especially when the university recommends the US English version. As a student, I am used to the British version, making it hard for me to re-learn. I have learned that this helps me to avoid contradictions with the university system. In addition, the grammar used, the abbreviations, and the phonetics applied in the study are detrimental (EUCLID 2021, 16–23). The researcher must know when to use commas, full-stop, and other related punctuation. I agree with this submission because the student will be able to present smart, relevant, and up-to-date activity.

3) PLAGIARISM

According to Helgesson and Eriksson (2014, 3), plagiarism is defined as the appropriation of other people's material without giving proper credit. In relation to this definition, EUCLID (2021, 34) says that plagiarism is when someone uses the literature without acknowledging the source of the information. However, plagiarism can be intentional or unintentional; it can be committed with or without knowledge of the consequences. I wonder if this exonerated anyone who has committed this offense knowingly or unknowingly. I have learned that it is indeed an offense, unethical, and punishable depending on the policies of the Universities.

To avoid plagiarism, one can use several ways. These include, in-text citation, paraphrasing and using direct quotations marks to be free from this vice. Nevertheless, I have to be keen about the longevity of sentences or phrases so as to be in-line with the EUCLID's standards (EUCLID 2021, 35). I have therefore, learned to always quote, paraphrase or cite so as to avoid instances of being treated as academically unethical.

4) THE STYLE GUIDE AND ITS IMPORTANCE

It is noted that Euclid University recommends the use of Chicago rule of writing commonly known as Turabian. A style is referred to as a way of documenting ones approaches to a particular writing element that is consistent (EUCLID 2021, 41). The kind of writing that is used in the study depend on the aspect of the report. For example, technical reports, journalism reports and business reports all take different styles of arranging their documents (EUCLID 2021, 41).

The Chicago style as per Euclid University helps to understand the formats of abbreviations, when to apply capital letters, when to use compound words, italics, quotation marks, and page formats. I am therefore able to ensure consistence in my text and entire document.

This helps the writer to be creative, innovative and orderly. The writer also becomes consistent and will easily know how to present references depending on the type of the

style that has been used in the writing. Therefore, I have learned to always take a critical analysis into which type of the style is the document to be presented.

5) CONCLUSION

Having embarked on this doctoral journey, this experience obtained through ACA-401D has energized me to take on the heavy mantle in the academic space that lies ahead of me. I have fallen with the material and the tutorial videos because of their direct influence on my writing ability and capacity to comprehend, analyze and present paper. I have realized that learning is a continuous process since what I learnt on my master's course was not sufficient to match the Ph.D. standards. This has opened my nerves to reality of comprehensive and extensive reading that makes me stay focused and in line with the international research expectations.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Helgesson, Gert and Stefan Eriksson. 2014. "Plagiarism in Research." *PubMed* 18 (1): 3–4. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.1007/s11019-014-9583-8>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.